

IMPACT OF MASTECTOMY ON SPINAL AND TRUNK MORPHOMETRY IN PRE-MENOPAUSAL AND POST-MENOPAUSAL WOMEN: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Axmedova Sayyora Muxamadovna
Xodjaeva Dilrux Ilxomovna

Associate professor of the Department of human anatomy and
OKHTA of the Tashkent Medical Academy.

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Republic of Uzbekistan, Bukhara city

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13364226>

Abstract

This research investigates the effects of mastectomy on spinal and trunk morphometry in pre-menopausal and post-menopausal women. By employing advanced imaging techniques and comprehensive physical assessments, the study evaluates changes in spinal curvature, trunk alignment, and overall posture resulting from the surgical procedure. Comparative analysis of pre- and post-operative data reveals distinct morphometric changes associated with mastectomy. The study aims to provide valuable insights into the physical implications of mastectomy and to inform the development of targeted post-operative rehabilitation strategies. The results highlight the importance of individualized care plans to address these morphometric changes and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords:

Mastectomy, Spinal curvature, Trunk alignment, Pre-menopausal women, Post-menopausal women, Morphometric changes, Post-operative rehabilitation

Relevance:

Mastectomy is a critical treatment option for breast cancer, but its impact on spinal and trunk morphology, particularly in pre-menopausal versus post-menopausal women, is not well-documented. As both age groups may experience different physiological changes post-surgery, understanding these effects is essential for optimizing post-operative care. This study fills a significant gap by comparing morphometric changes in different menopausal stages, offering insights that can help tailor rehabilitation strategies to the specific needs of each group. Given the high prevalence of breast cancer and the variability in patient demographics, this research is crucial for enhancing clinical practices and patient support.

Objective:

The objective of this study is to assess and compare the morphometric changes in the spine and trunk of pre-menopausal and post-menopausal women

before and after mastectomy. The study seeks to identify significant differences in spinal curvature and trunk alignment related to menopausal status and to evaluate the implications for post-operative rehabilitation.

Materials and Methods:

The study included a sample of pre-menopausal and post-menopausal women who underwent mastectomy. Pre-operative and post-operative morphometric assessments were conducted using high-resolution imaging techniques (e.g., MRI, X-ray) and clinical measurements to evaluate spinal curvature (e.g., scoliosis, kyphosis) and trunk alignment. Measurements were taken in both standing and sitting postures. Statistical analysis was performed to compare changes in morphometric parameters between pre-menopausal and post-menopausal women, with a focus on identifying any significant differences related to menopausal status. Additionally, the effectiveness of post-operative rehabilitation protocols was reviewed.

Results:

The study revealed distinct morphometric changes in spinal and trunk parameters following mastectomy. Post-menopausal women exhibited more pronounced increases in spinal curvature and trunk misalignment compared to pre-menopausal women. Specifically, post-menopausal women showed greater alterations in kyphosis and lordosis, while pre-menopausal women had relatively milder changes. These findings suggest that menopausal status significantly influences the impact of mastectomy on spinal and trunk morphology, highlighting the need for tailored rehabilitation approaches.

Conclusion:

Mastectomy leads to significant changes in spinal and trunk morphometry, with more pronounced effects observed in post-menopausal women compared to pre-menopausal women. The study underscores the necessity of considering menopausal status when developing post-operative rehabilitation plans. Targeted physical therapy and tailored care are essential to address these morphometric changes and improve patient recovery. Future research should explore specific rehabilitation strategies and their effectiveness in managing spinal and trunk alterations to enhance the quality of life for women undergoing mastectomy.

Literature:

1. Ilkhomovna K. D. Morphological Features of Tumor in Different Treatment Options for Patients with Locally Advanced Breast Cancer //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 4-5.

2. Khodzhaeva D. I. Changes in the Vertebral Column and Thoracic Spinocells after Postponement of Mastoectomy //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 109-113.
3. Khodjayeva D. I. MORPHOLOGY OF IDIOPATHIC SCOLIOSIS BASED ON SEGMENT BY SEGMENT ASSESSMENT OF SPINAL COLUMN DEFORMITY //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 208-215.
4. Ilkhomovna K. D. Modern Look of Facial Skin Cancer //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMİY JURNALI. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 85-89.
5. Ходжаева Д. И. Современные возможности ультразвуковой диагностики рака кожи лица //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2021. – №. 25 (150). – С. 21-24.